

ANALYSIS OF OPTIMAL HYDROGEN-RICH REFINERY OFFGAS UTILIZATION

Mierka O., Variny M.

Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak university of Technology in Bratislava, Radlinského 9, 812 37 Bratislava, Slovak republic
GRUCON s.r.o., Nezábudková 24, 821 01 Bratislava, Slovak republic
miroslav.variny@stuba.sk

Introduction

In a refinery, hydrogen supply, quality and management of its production costs and utilization efficiency contributes significantly to the overall crude refining costs. Commonly the heavy gasoline platforming and steam methane (natural gas) reforming (SMR) contribute mostly to the refinery hydrogen pool, the latter usually being its marginal source¹. Even in case the given steam reforming process can accept only light hydrocarbons as feed (e.g. the pre-reformer is absent), various hydrogen-rich refinery offgases (ROGs) can be utilized in this process, thus partially replacing the natural gas feed²⁻⁴. ROGs can alternatively be processed in a separate PSA (or membrane) unit, or fed to the refinery fuel gas network⁵.

The analysis of optimal ROGs utilization always has to consider local media (natural gas, water steam, electric energy) prices as well as any technologic, capacity, reliability, hydrogen purity etc. constraints^{6,7}. Questions that need to be correctly answered include following:

- Which of the available alternatives enables to produce most hydrogen? (In case the hydrogen production capacity is or is to become the refinery's bottleneck in the near future.)
- What is the impact of each of the alternatives on the refinery's overall natural gas (NG) consumption both from qualitative and quantitative point of view? (Natural gas usually is both the marginal hydrogen production feed as well as the marginal refinery's fuel gas pool contributor)
- What is the impact each of the alternatives on the refinery's overall steam balance? (The SMR usually is a net steam exporter.)
- How does the resulting refinery's steam balance shift further impact the refinery's fuel and electricity costs? (E.g. what is the marginal steam source for the refinery and what type of fuel does it use? Is it just a steam source or a cogeneration unit? Or, in case there is excess steam in the refinery, how does the refinery's steam balance shift influence its marginal utilization? – F.e. on purpose electricity production in condensing steam turbines, or excess steam venting into the atmosphere.)
- Is there an impact of each of the alternatives on the overall refinery's electric energy consumption and if yes, what is its magnitude?
- What is the true marginal cost of each of the media whose balances are impacted?

We thus see that, due to the possible study complexity, a correct balance border construction is essential as each of the above mentioned aspects exclusion from the balancing process may seriously deform the resulting economic balance^{8,9}. The second, equally crucial step is to determine the correct calculation basis for all analyzed alternatives meaning that in all considered calculation cases:

- The total amount of hydrogen supplied to its consumers is the same;
- The refinery's fuel gas network is balanced in terms of the total fuel lower heating value, e.g. if any of the considered alternatives increases or decreases the fuel gas production and/or consumption, the balance has to be restored by the respective marginal fuel consumption change;
- The refinery's steam network is balanced in terms of total steam enthalpy (the applied balancing principle is the same as in the fuel gas case);
- The refinery's electric energy balance needs to reflect each change imposed on it both from its production (side effect of steam balance shift on cogenerated mechanical or electric energy) and consumption point of view (changes in electric energy consumption due to more/less intense operation of any significant compressor, blower, pump etc. included in the balance borders)

This contribution aims at providing an analysis procedure of optimal ROGs utilization by means of a case study, considering the above aspects, each to the extent they deserve. In order to objectivize the calculation procedure, the SMR design and operating data were used separately and the obtained results were compared.

System understudy

The analyzed system is depicted in the Figure 1. The correct balance borders have been constructed in compliance with the aspects listed in the Introduction. The system specification is as follows:

- The ROGs from two individual production units, containing 5 to 10 % wt. hydrogen and over 60 % wt. of C2 and higher hydrocarbons can either be fed to the SMR unit or to an independent PSA units or (exceptionally) directly to the fuel gas network;
- The SMR unit is the marginal hydrogen producer;
- NG is both the marginal feed to the SMR unit and to the fuel gas network;
- The SMR unit is a significant steam exporter, mostly on the high pressure (3.5 MPa) level; the marginal source of steam is the combined steam and power plant (CSPP) that produces very high pressure steam (9 MPa) that is expanded in steam turbines to different pressure levels and exported to the refinery whereby electric energy is cogenerated;
- The refinery consumes all electric energy produced in the CSPP and imports the rest from the outer grid

Figure 1. Schematic depiction of the system under study

Let us define two possible operational states, based on Figure 1:

- ROGs are fed to the SMR unit, serving as co-feed with NG
- SMR unit operates solely with NG feed; ROGs are processed in an independent PSA unit operating with 75% hydrogen recovery efficiency; PSA offgas is routed to refinery's fuel gas network

These two operational state possibilities are analyzed from the point of design as well as operational data point of view.

Design data analysis

In following Tables I and II we provide key parameters and input data needed to perform calculation procedure based almost solely on SMR unit design data. As is obvious, the two SMR unit design states #1 and #2 exhibit the same reactor outlet temperature and almost the same steam to process ratio that are the two most important adjustable operational parameters. Except for feed composition both design states operate under almost the same conditions and can therefore serve as platform for comparison.

In order to recalculate the SMR design state #1 operational parameters to lower hydrogen production, one cannot use specific values but has to use the marginal ones. As the design documentation does not include other operational states from which the needed marginal values could be calculated, we had to extract them from operational data (natural gas consumption and steam export) that were plotted against net produced hydrogen. The data sets were fitted with linear dependences; the slopes of the linear fits representing the marginal values. Obtained marginal values are listed in the lower part of Table I. Are the ROGs fed to the independent PSA unit, they can be split into (virtually pure 99.9% vol.) hydrogen stream and PSA offgas. The material balance of the PSA unit is provided in Table II.

Table I. SMR unit design parameters and marginal values of NG consumption and steam export

Operational parameter	SMR design state #1: pure NG feed	SMR design state #2: NG + ROG mixture feed
Reactor outlet temperature, °C	850	850
Steam to process gas ratio, t/t	3.299	3.304
Net hydrogen produced, t/h	3.475	3.475
NG consumption (feed + extra fuel for SMR furnace), t/h	13.065	7.561
ROGs feed t/h	0	4.696
3.5 MPa / 0.4 MPa steam export, t/h	42.206 / 3.015	36.564 / 3.556
Marginal SMR unit values obtained by operational data linear regression; with pure NG feed to the SMR unit; per 1 ton of net hydrogen produced		
Natural gas consumption	4.42 tons	
Steam (3.5 + 0.4 MPa) export	18.5 tons (56.5 GJ)	

Table II. ROGs mixture composition and material balance of its processing in the independent PSA unit. Considered natural gas lower heating value is 48.86 GJ/t and its composition in % vol. as follows: Methane 96.66; Ethane 1.57; Propane 0.47; C4 and higher 0.2; Carbon dioxide 0.24; Nitrogen 0.84

Constituent, kg/h	ROG mixture feed	Hydrogen from PSA unit	PSA offgas
Hydrogen	371.0	285.7	85.3
Methane / Ethane	1127.9 / 1036.7	-	1127.9 / 1036.7
Propane / Butanes	1086.1 / 701.8	-	1086.1 / 701.8
C5 and higher / Inerts	370.0 / 2.5	-	370.0 / 2.5
Total	4696.0	285.7	4410.3
NG equivalent in lower heating value, kg/h	5098.3	699.0	4399.3

Table III. Comparison of **A.** and **B.** states. Employed prices: NG 430 €/t; 3.5 MPa steam 32 €/t; 0.4 MPa steam 22 €/t. Steam prices already incorporate the cogenerated electric energy value in the CSPP

Operational parameter / state	A.	B.
Net hydrogen production, t/h	3.475	3.189 + 0.286 = 3.475
Natural gas fed to SMR unit (feed + extra fuel), t/h	7.561	11.802
Produced PSA unit offgas NG equivalent, t/h	-	4.399
NG total consumption, t/h	7.561	11.802 - 4.399 = 7.403
Δ NG total consumption B. minus A. , t/h		7.403 - 7.561 = -0.158
3.5 MPa steam export from the SMR unit, t/h	36.564	36.92
Δ 3.5 MPa steam export B. minus A. , t/h		36.92 - 36.564 = +0.356
0.4 MPa steam export from the SMR unit, t/h	3.556	3.015
Δ 0.4 MPa steam export B. minus A. , t/h		3.015 - 3.556 = -0.541
Variable hydrogen production cost B. minus A. , €/h		+ 64

Since in both cases the same amount of hydrogen is to be generated (3.745 t/h), from Tables I,II it is obvious, that the SMR unit needs to produce just $3.475 - 0.286 = 3.189$ t/h in **B.**. The SMR unit operation parameters at 3.189 t/h net hydrogen production are derived from Table 1, using the design state #1 definition and the SMR marginal operational parameters. F.e. the total natural gas consumption in the SMR unit at 3.189 t/h hydrogen production can thus be calculated as follows: NG consumption = $13.065 \text{ t/h} - 4.42 \text{ t/t} \cdot (3.475 - 3.189) \text{ t/h} = 11.802 \text{ t/h}$. In the same manner, the net 3.5 MPa steam export (supposing the 0.4 MPa steam export does not change) at 3.189 t/h hydrogen production is as follows: $42.206 \text{ t/h} - 18.5 \text{ t/t} \cdot (3.475 - 3.189) \text{ t/h} = 36.92 \text{ t/h}$.

The following Table 3 provides the comparison between the 3.475 t/h hydrogen production by the operational state **A.** and **B.**. Obviously, both hydrogen AND PSA offgas are produced in **B.**, whereas only hydrogen is produced in **A.**. Thus the PSA offgas value in form of NG heating equivalent has to be incorporated into calculations as an extra NG stream lowering the NG consumption in **B.**

As appears from Table 3, **state B.**, compared to **A.**, is accompanied by lower natural gas consumption and slightly lower total steam export while keeping the net produced hydrogen flow the same. Expressed in financial terms and using the model prices of energy media, hydrogen production by **B.**, compared to **A.**, is cheaper by 64 €/h, e.g. it is cheaper to produce hydrogen from pure natural gas and process the ROGs in the

independent PSA unit. Obviously this difference would further increase if the PSA efficiency were higher. Recently, after adsorbent change, the given PSA efficiency has been reported to increase to 85 %, that in the considered case would enable to recover additional 37 kg/h of hydrogen resulting in additional 10 €/h benefit. The fact itself that feeding ROGs to SMR unit, instead of their separation in the independent PSA unit is economically unfavorable is perhaps a bit surprising but it can be effectively explained considering the stoichiometry and equilibrium data for the light hydrocarbons steam reforming:

- Per 1kg of produced hydrogen, consumption of C2 and higher hydrocarbons is higher than that of methane (natural gas), due to lowering hydrogen content with increasing number of carbon atoms;
- Per 1kg of produced hydrogen, steam reforming of C2 and higher hydrocarbons consumes more water steam than in the case of methane (natural gas) reforming;
- Hydrogen present in the ROGs shifts the reaction equilibrium back towards the reactants

Operational data analysis

The long term operational parameters of the SMR unit understudy differ from design: lower reactor outlet temperature (790 to 820 °C) and a somewhat higher steam to process gas ratio (appr. 3.6) is applied. In order to confirm the results obtained from comparing design states by real SMR unit operational states analysis, we processed the operational states in the same manner as described above, with minor adjustments. The data provided were in form of daily averages, comprising all relevant calculation inputs including the amount and composition of ROGs processed in the SMR unit. The calculation procedure is shown in Table IV.

Table IV. Calculations example based on operational data.*: 11.9 €/h have been subtracted, representing the by appr. 0.54 t/h lower design 0.4 MPa steam export (see Table 3) in **B.**, compared to **A.**

Operational parameter / date	22.8.2010	29.10.2010
Net hydrogen produced, t/h	2.779	2.749
NG consumption (feed + extra fuel for SMR furnace), t/h	11.288	9.565
ROGs feed; hydrogen content, t/h	0	1.473 ; 0.174
3.5 MPa steam export, t/h	36.61	35.49
Hydrogen obtainable in the independent PSA unit; PSA offgas NG equivalent, t/h	0.131; 1.305	
Adjusted 22.8.2010 operational state (= B.), matching the 29.10.2010 state (= A.)		
Hydrogen to be produced in the SMR, t/h	2.749 – 0.131 = 2.618	
Adjusted NG consumption, t/h	11.288 – 4.42.(2.779-2.618) = 10.576	
NG consumption incl. the PSA offgas credit, t/h	10.576 – 1.305 = 9.271	
Adjusted 3.5 MPa steam export, t/h	36.61 – 18.5.(2.779-2.618) = 33.63	
Comparison of B. vs. A.		
Δ NG total consumption B. minus A. , t/h	9.271 – 9.565 = -0.294	
Δ 3.5 MPa steam export B. minus A. , t/h	33.63 – 35.49 = -1.86	
Variable hydrogen production cost B. minus A. , €/h*	55.0	

Generally the operational data analysis comprises:

- A longer time period comprising days $D_{1...n}$ has been chosen when the ROGs have been processed in the SMR unit (thus representing operational states $A_{1...n}$);
- An adjacent time period comprising days $D_{1...m}$ has been defined when the SMR unit has been operated solely on NG feed
- For a chosen i-th day from $D_{1...n}$ period (representing the A_i state) and a chosen j-th day from $D_{1...m}$ the j-th day SMR unit operational parameters have been adjusted to match hydrogen production from i-th day, lowered by the hydrogen that could be produced in the independent PSA unit on the i-th day. This adjusted D_j operation defines the operational state B_j .
- Comparison of B_j vs. A_i state yields differences ΔNG_{ij} and $\Delta steam_{ij}$ and thus the financial effect F_{ij} representing the variable hydrogen production costs difference

Average values $\overline{\Delta NG}$; $\overline{\Delta Steam}$ were obtained by averaging all differences ΔNG_{ij} and $\Delta steam_{ij}$ over i and j (1a,b),

whereby in the end the average financial effect $\overline{F_{ij}}$ was obtained:

$$\overline{\Delta NG} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \Delta NG_{ij}}{n.m}; \quad \overline{\Delta Steam} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \Delta Steam_{ij}}{n.m} \quad (1a,b)$$

The following Figure 2. shows the financial effects F_{ij} for $i = 29.10.2010$. Its aim is to show that even within a period when the SMR unit operates purely on NG, the variable hydrogen production costs vary within ± 60 €/h (or appr. ± 20 €/t produced hydrogen) that indicates the influence of other operational parameters and certainly would merit further attention. It also includes autocorrelation of operational data within the $D_{1...n}$ period, that show a similar pattern, but their values are lower by some 50 to 60 €/h on average.

Figure 2. Financial effects F_{ij} for $i = 28.10.2010$. Solid dots: $D_{1...m}$ period; open dots: $D_{1...n}$ period

Table V. Results of operational data analysis for three individual time periods characterized by SMR unit operation solely on NG compared to ROGs coprocessing in the 20.10.2010 – 30.11.2010 period

Parameter	31.7.2010 – 18.10.2010	1.12.2010 – 26.3.2011	23.4.2011 – 22.6.2011	20.10.2010 – 30.11.2010
Average SMR unit hydrogen production, kg/h	2686	2686	3029	2711
Average reactor outlet temperature, °C	799	798	807	799
Average steam to process gas ratio, t/t	3.61	3.65	3.59	3.57
$\overline{\Delta NG}$, t/h	-0.280	-0.140	-0.224	-
$\overline{\Delta Steam}$, t/h	-1.51	-0.4	-1.42	-
$\overline{\Delta FE}$, €/h	+61	+37	+40	-

Table V. shows comparison of three individual time periods when the SMR unit has been operated solely on NG with the 20.10.2010 to 30.11.2010 when the ROGs have been coprocessed in the SMR unit. These three periods are characterized by varying process parameters, however in all three cases it is obvious, that pure NG operation of the SMR unit yields lower hydrogen production costs compared to ROGs coprocessing.

It can be concluded that both in case of design data analysis and operational data evaluation, the obtained impact of ROGs coprocessing on the SMR unit operation is similar: pure NG operation means lower total natural gas consumption and lower steam export. In financial terms the hydrogen production by pure NG operation and ROGs processing in the independent PSA unit is by 40 to 60 €/h less costly than that of ROGs coprocessing in the SMR unit.

Due to limited space exhaustive electric energy balance is not provided. Its preliminary analysis yields the conclusion, that the electric energy costs related to the problem under study do not play an important role in the variable hydrogen production costs. The calculated electric energy difference between state **B.** and **A.** obtained from the design state analysis is in the order of tens of kW. As the electric energy consumption in the main process equipment within the balance borders is not measured separately, no quantitative conclusions can be drawn related to operational electric energy consumption difference between **B.** and **A.**

Conclusions

This contribution aims at elucidating the key importance of correct balance borders settings and correct calculation base construction. In order to demonstrate this necessity a case study bearing on analysis of

optimal hydrogen rich refinery offgases utilization is presented here. The ROG's can either be fed to the SMR unit, represented by operational state **A.** or be processed in a separate PSA unit in operational state **B.** In both cases hydrogen is produced, however in the second one a valuable by-product is obtained in form of PSA offgas. The correct economic calculation includes hydrogen and fuel gas network balancing as well as correct calculation of steam export change from the SMR unit. In the calculation process, marginal values of natural gas consumption and steam export are made use of. Both the analysis of design SMR unit operational state and operational data analysis confirm that the ROG's utilization in a separate PSA unit is economically favorable over their feeding to the SMR unit. The typical benefit resulting from preferential **B.** operation ranges between 40 and 60 €/h for the considered media prices, resulting from lower overall NG consumption and lower steam export. Such result can qualitatively be explained by combining the reaction stoichiometry, as ethane and higher hydrocarbons present in the ROG's produce less hydrogen and consume more steam per hydrocarbon unit, compared to methane or natural gas. Moreover due to the chemical equilibrium principle the hydrogen present in the ROG's acts against additional hydrogen formation in steam reforming process.

Only the results of electric energy balance are presented in this paper due to limited space; they indicate that it does play only minor role in variable hydrogen production costs and would thus affect the above financial effect only in terms of several €/h.

It must be remembered that **A.**, e.g. feeding the ROG's to the SMR unit at the same time means decrease of maximal hydrogen production capacity in the refinery: the design SMR unit cases enable 3.475 t/h hydrogen production both from pure NG and from ROG's and NG mixture. In case **B.** the ROG's are processed in the separate PSA unit, increasing the hydrogen production capacity by up to nearly 300 kg/h.

Concludingly there is one other aspect that deserves attention: the C₂ and higher hydrocarbons in the ROG's have been assigned value only as NG fuel substitute. However these might represent an interesting and valuable feed f.e. for ethylene production in the adjacent Steam Cracker unit if separated from the ROG's. In this case their value would be higher than their fuel value and would significantly contribute to preferential use of **B.** operation over **A.** Recently a project aimed at valuable C₂ and higher hydrocarbons recovery has been launched in the refinery, counting with the offgases from the separate PSA unit as one of their important sources. It is thus expected that the operation **A.** will be preferred only in extraordinary cases for very short periods, on the contrary to its preferential use in the past.

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